

Nutrient digestibility of three different batches of *Hermetia illucens* in European sea bass

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In this study, the digestibility of three partially defatted *Hermetia illucens* meals, produced by the same company in three different batches, was assessed by replacing 30% of a reference diet in European sea bass *Dicentrarchus labrax*.

Minor differences were observed in the protein and energy content of the three insect meals, while more prominent differences were observed in the fat and ash content. The incorporation of insect meals in the reference diet led to increased protein content and decreased fat content in the resulting diets.

Overall, the apparent digestibility of the diets containing the three different insect meals was similar. No differences were observed in the dry matter and protein digestibility between the reference diet and the insect meal diets, while the energy digestibility of two of the three insect meal diets was higher compared to the reference diet. The fat digestibility of all the insect diets was higher, probably due to the defatted nature of the insect meals which resulted in lower fat content of the diets.

Regarding the digestibility of the test ingredients, the different insect meals had similar dry matter, protein, fat and energy digestibility.

In summary, the overall digestibility of the three different *Hermetia illucens* meals was similar. The inclusion of 30% of *Hermetia illucens* meal in the diet of European sea bass, improved fat and energy digestibility without affecting dry matter and protein digestibility.